

TRANSDISCIPLINARY LEARNING OVER TRADITIONAL LEARNING

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Abstract :

Traditional approach of education is more of theoretical than practical. Many times students learn new concepts only theoretically and practical approach is missing and also curriculum is also limited to one discipline. But transdisciplinary learning goes beyond subject specialization and connects with other disciplines. It touches different subjects and broadens the depth of knowledge. Hence this study is undertaken to find out best learning method out of traditional and transdisciplinary learning. For the purpose of study, primary data collection method is used and response of 214 students is collected through questionnaire. This research also helps to know students' view about implementation of transdisciplinary learning.

Key words: *Transdisciplinary education, Traditional education, domain, multi-skill*

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Introduction :

In traditional approach of education, many times students learn new concepts only theoretically. Curriculum is also designed in such a way that teachers only explain, share pictures, videos but practical experience is missing specifically in commerce and arts faculty. Teachers complete syllabus in stipulated time which has limited scope for experiments. In traditional education, most of the time lecture method is used even for practical subjects. Similarly focus is only on one subject or discipline. In today's competitive era, it is necessary to have good knowledge of domain as well as basic knowledge of other disciplines related to domain. Students not only need hand-on training but also want to learn from own experience and test their capabilities. With increase in interdependency or interconnectivity of various subjects, there is a need to bring significant changes in teaching learning method. With the changing environment, technology and industry requirements, it is necessary to make significant changes in learning methods too. We know the popular say "Jack of all, master of none" but now it is to be modified as "Jack of all, master of one". Today multi-tasking and multi-skilled people are looked upon by an organization for fast growth of business. Hence it becomes important to introduce innovative teaching learning techniques to connect students and topic. One of the solutions is to move to transdisciplinary learning which means same concept explaining in a practical way and by connecting with other disciplines. Simply it is going beyond one's specialization and integrating various subjects for better understanding of domain subject. It is also highlighted in New Education Policy, 2020. This would

also explore students with new ideas and arouse interest about topic among them. For example, science students can learn accountancy subject and can understand profit and loss statement of the organization. They can also develop managerial skills by leaning management subject. Similarly commerce students can learn psychology subject to understand customers, suppliers, employees psychology. Thus learning subjects beyond their specializations can make them versatile. Also along with theoretical knowledge, practical experience is more important. Students should be able to apply their knowledge and skills in real life situations and for this deep understanding of concepts as well as self-confidence is necessary. They should be able to link different subjects to upgrade and upskill themselves. Thus transdisciplinary learning plays important role in education.

Review of literature :

Carmen-Gabriela Boston (2014) conducted research of teachers and students from 7th & 8th standard students by making two sample of schools having poor results and good results. It was studied that transdisciplinary curriculum was missing in current practice. Also students need to develop theoretical knowledge to adopt transdisciplinary learning. Teachers also took interest in the same. Students agreed with the necessity of new learning method.

Inese Jurgena and Dagnija Cedere and Ingrida Kevisa (2018) conducted research on 9th standard students from 17 schools who participated in the survey. It is found that participants were not much interested in the subjects. They faced difficulties in evaluating development of student's interest in the subjects. But students enjoyed discussions and laboratory work. Schools are not ready completely to paradigm shift to transdisciplinary approach. It is concluded that students have potential to study and understand the subjects with new learning techniques

Vinciane Servantie, Bart Van Hoof, Maria Fernanda Salamanca (2019) conducted research in the form of case study of one academic company providing management consulting services. Company applied different mechanisms to implement transdisciplinary approach in five phrases. From the 12 years' experience of the program and based on its clients' feedback, it is concluded that initially clients did not accept the concept fully but gradually they approved the proposal. Students interacted with each other and constructed knowledge based on personal experience.

Burcu Gurkan (2021) conducted research on 50 teachers from University of Turkey. The aim of the study was to check positive and negative experience of teacher through a model transdisciplinary integrated curriculum designed. Teachers faced problems in planning and evaluating process. It also helped in teachers' skill development which were also visible. The model bought systematic approach and also co-operation among teachers of different disciplines. Gap analysis – From above literature review, it is observed that all research papers were published by foreign researchers. It means hardly any research on transdisciplinary learning is conducted in India. Above researchers have developed model or conducted experiment after implementing transdisciplinary learning in curriculum. Hence researcher has selected such unexplored topic and attempted to find out students' satisfaction about current traditional curriculum and perception about transdisciplinary learning if imparted in curriculum.

Objectives :

Following are the objectives of research study:

1. To understand the concept of transdisciplinary learning.
2. To know the advantages and challenges in implementing transdisciplinary learning.
3. To find out students' perception towards the concept of transdisciplinary learning.
4. To find out best learning method out of traditional learning and transdisciplinary learning.

Research Methodology :

For this study, primary data collection method was used. Data was collected from 214 students of DBJ College, Chiplun pursuing commerce degree by sending a link of google form on students' whatsapp group. The researcher has applied convenient sampling method for the study. Various parameters were studied on five point likert scale and to summarize the data, percentage method was used.

Data Analysis :

1. Satisfaction about current traditional curriculum :

70% of the students are satisfied with current traditional curriculum. Their opinion may change on experiencing transdisciplinary learning. It shows that rest of the students need change in curriculum.

2. Satisfaction about current pattern of examination (Both online & Offline) :

85% of the students are satisfied with current examination pattern because they are very much comfortable with online exam and good results. In case of theoretical offline exam also, they generally study before examination. May be there is less urge of knowledge gaining or fear of continuous evaluation.

3. Teaching learning method currently used in the classroom :

Here maximum number of students agreed upon lecture method and PPT presentation which is supported by limited discussion and interaction. It shows that curriculum of traditional learning has a little scope for case study, hand on training and practical sessions.

4. Current curriculum and teaching learning method helps to develop skills:

69% of the students are able to develop skills from current curriculum and teaching learning method. Definitely it helps in developing basic skills and theoretical knowledge but in today's competitive world, multidisciplinary, multi-tasking, multi skills are more important.

5. More weightage should be given to practical exposure than just theoretical knowledge:

Majority of the students agreed on this and hence transdisciplinary learning becomes more relevant.

6. Ability to apply existing knowledge and skills in real life situation :

85% of the students think that they are able to apply existing knowledge and skills in real life. But the fact is that they have not faced much practical difficulties in life or there have less interactions with outer world.

7. Implementing transdisciplinary (subjects beyond your specialization) learning in the curriculum :

84% of the students wants to get connected with other disciplines and learn new things to develop deeper understanding of the concept.

8. Transdisciplinary learning will help in better job/career opportunity :

83% of the students have understood that traditional learning lacks practical exposure whereas transdisciplinary learning can help in better job prospects.

9. Advantages of implementing transdisciplinary learning :

Majority of the students agreed upon various advantages of transdisciplinary learning specifically better understanding and skill development.

10. Challenges in implementing transdisciplinary learning :

Majority of students also agree upon various challenges that they will have to face in transdisciplinary learning specifically active participation and developing learning attitude among them.

11. Transdisciplinary learning is better than traditional learning:

73% of the students accept that transdisciplinary learning is better than traditional learning considering various advantages of transdisciplinary learning.

12. Perception towards transdisciplinary Learning:

Majority of the students agreed upon more reading, efforts, updating knowledge and well preparation before lectures which will result in overall personality development.

13. Right examination pattern for complete assessment of student :

Majority of the students realized that project work and practical exam along with theory paper are necessary for their complete assessment.

Limitations of the study :

1. Data was collected from one college only and study covers only commerce students.
2. Only students study was undertaken and teachers' perception is not covered.
3. Study is conducted without conducting practical experiments of transdisciplinary learning.

Conclusion :

Traditional approach of education is more of theoretical than practical. From the study, it is found that students are satisfied with existing curriculum and examination pattern but they also realized the need of practical exposure in competitive world which has very little scope in traditional learning. Hence some vocational courses shall be designed. Current evaluation system promotes mugging up, memorizing things than intelligence. It is also unable to appreciate creativity. Hence project work, practical exam can support theory exam for complete assessment of students. Further it is suggested that for effective implementation of transdisciplinary learning, all teachers shall collaborate and work in a team. Teachers must shift away from their comfort zone of specialization and also from culture of working individually. But they shall share ideas with teachers from other disciplines and integrate learning experience. Similarly students also need to be engaged and involved in studies and prepare themselves purposefully. Transdisciplinary learning

shall be implemented from school level which will help to navigate the world of ideas and create better career opportunities as well as increase the skills to handle real life situations. Students will learn to create knowledge through self-regulated learning. Thus it is concluded that Transdisciplinary learning is better than traditional learning.

Scope for Further Research :

This research can be taken further at higher level to find out students as well as teachers' opinion about transdisciplinary learning. For effective outcome, implementation of transdisciplinary learning, experiments, techniques is necessary. Also awareness about transdisciplinary learning can be created as very less research is conducted on this topic in India. Comparison between traditional and transdisciplinary learning can be done effectively.

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